

Type and level of production provided by the requestor

Type of production: Broiler; Other poultry

Level: Husbandry; Breeding

Keywords: Behaviour; Housing system; Management

Background context provided by the requestor

In the legislation for housing of broiler breeders in Sweden (attached) there is a paragraph (Chapter 4, 5§) stating that all breeders shall have access to perches or elevated platforms. The elevated area shall be large enough for all birds being able to sit there at the same time. There is a recommendation that the elevated area shouldn't be smaller than 160 cm²/kg for birds between 1,6-3,0 kg and not smaller than 115 cm²/kg for birds between 3-5 kg. This recommendation is now questioned by the industry. In the EFSA report "Welfare of broilers on farm" from December 2022 one of the actions mentioned as urgent to apply to improve the welfare of broiler breeders is to give the animals access to perches and/or elevated structures. The report states that data about perch use of broiler breeders are scarce but due to body dimensions it is mentioned that a broiler breeder would need 21 cm (female) -22 cm (male) perch length. For broilers, elevated platforms are used better than perches, but the report states that more research is needed to estimate the minimal space required for elevated platforms for preventing resting problems etc.

Question raised by the requestor

We would like to know:

1. Are all breeders (or breeders and broilers) motivated to sit on elevated platform all together and when (day and night)?
2. What would be the optimal elevated platform that fulfil the needs of these animals for sitting in an elevated position/roosting? Can you provide some indication of the minimum space needed (per broiler or kg) to sit in an elevated platform?

Answer

Introduction

Resting problems are among major welfare issues in broilers and broiler breeders (EFSA, 2023). Normal resting behaviour of chickens is, under natural conditions, performed off the ground (Wood-Gush et al., 1978 in EFSA, 2023), whereas broilers and breeders are mainly reared in floor systems without access to elevated structure to roost and rest. Broiler breeders in rearing and lay are highly motivated to roost in an elevated area (Gebhardt-Henrich et al., 2017) and strongly favor the highest structures (Gebhardt-Henrich et al., 2014 in Gebhardt-Henrich et al., 2017). Moreover, studies have shown that, in addition to improving resting conditions, elevated structures decrease the risk of locomotory and leg problems in broilers (Mocz et al. 2022; EFSA, 2023).

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Although, perches are well-used by slow-growing strains, they are less frequented by faster growing broilers because their large breast muscles impair their balance and their poor mobility makes it harder to access elevated structures (de Jong et al., 2019, 2021; Bailie et al., 2018). In contrast, elevated platforms are well-used by all types of chickens, especially if access ramps are available (Malchow et al., 2019). Providing ramps may also be advisable due to the decline in perch use by broiler breeders as they age (from about 50 to 20% according to Gebhardt-Henrich et al. (2017)), potentially related to an increasing difficulty to reach high perches. In terms of perch design, Ross 308 parent-stock broilers have demonstrated a preference for elevated platforms over rounded perches, and for rubber-coated over metal perches until late lay (Baxter & O'Connell, 2025). However, the research on perch preferences in broiler breeders is lacking and preference can be influenced by numerous factors such as the height, material, and other management factors.

The absence or insufficient availability of elevated structures, such as platforms, may cause frustration of the birds due to the lack of three-dimensional resting structures as well as competition (EFSA, 2023). As for every type of environmental enrichments, it is hard to determine how much elevated platform or perches are needed for a defined number of birds and no studies have determined a minimum number of elevated structures for a flock of broilers. However, information on the size of the birds and their behavioural motivation related to such structures could help to resolve this issue.

Birds' roosting behaviour and motivation

Based on the study of Spindler et al. (2016), Ross broiler breeder females occupy an average of 514 cm² per bird (or 0.14 cm²/g BW) when squatting at the end of production (58-60 weeks, approx. 4141 g), and males occupy an average of 805 cm² per bird (or 0.18 cm²/g BW) when squatting at the end of production (58-60 weeks, approx. 4721 g). These data can be multiplied by the number of birds to estimate the adequate elevated surface that allows all the birds to roost on a platform at the same time. However, it should be noted that this estimate does not account for the preferred inter-individual distance between birds. Indeed, inter-individual distance is important to take into account because a conspecific that is too close to an animal may be interpreted as an aversive stimulus (Buijs et al. 2011). However, this inter-individual distance is not fixed, and it is influenced by several parameters such as the stocking density. Broilers stocked at a very low density (2.4 birds/m², in a study with low group size and small pens (Buijs et al. 2011)) could be attracted to each other whereas at higher densities (≥ 15 kg/m² or around 6 birds/m²) they started to experience the proximity of conspecifics as aversive (Buijs, 2011). The inter-individual distance can also be related to the behaviour expressed. In the study from Buijs et al. (2011), broilers were further from their nearest neighbor when eating or drinking than when adjusting their sitting or lying posture, foraging or preening, although these data need to be interpreted cautiously due to the low occurrence of certain behaviours according to the authors.

Regarding perches, perch use at night depends on the length of perch available per broiler breeder (Gebhardt-Henrich et al., 2017). In the study of Gebhardt-Henrich et al. (2017), more Ross 308 broiler breeders were perched at night when at least 14 cm perch length per bird was provided than with less available perch length. And, in the study of Baxter and O'Connell (2025) across the production period, the increase in number of birds (Ross 308 parent-stock, mixed-sex) perching slowed once there was less than 23 cm of perch length per bird, suggesting that this represents the minimum perch length per bird needed to maximize perch utilization.

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Beyond the individual space needed for birds to roost on elevated structures, the birds' behaviour, and especially their use of perches and platforms, need to be considered to determine the minimum surface area required to prevent resting problems. Perch occupancy has been reported as 74% of maximum occupancy per perch during the night and 39% during the day in broiler breeders on platform perches across the laying period (Baxter & O'Connell, 2025). Nighttime occupancy reached or exceeded maximum in 27% of observations whereas maximum occupancy was reached or exceeded in only 2% of daytime observations (Baxter & O'Connell, 2025). Similarly, Brandes et al. (2020) reported a mean perch occupancy (across seven different perch types) in broiler breeders of 0.73 ± 0.86 birds/m during the daytime, and 2.07 ± 1.54 birds/m in the nighttime (maximum occupancy of 5.90 birds/m for both day and night). However, it should be noted that patterns of occupancy are influenced by the structure and material of the perch (Baxter & O'Connell, 2025).

Conclusions

Roosting on a high elevated structure is a fundamental behavioural need of broilers and broiler breeders, especially at night. Many parameters must be taken into account in determination of the space needed on the elevated structures such as the size of the birds, the inter-individual distance depending on the stocking density and the time budget of the birds. Other important factors for the use of the elevated structures are the material and the accessibility of the elevated structures (presence or absence of access ramps), in particular for heavy and older birds. For these reasons, it is not possible to quantify space allowance on elevated platforms without specifying the scenario and making some assumptions. However, a possibility would be to estimate the minimum space allowance on elevated structures based on the body dimensions of the given category of bird, keeping in mind that the majority of the flock will be motivated to roost at night and that an inter-individual distance, size yet to be determined, is likely preferred.

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